

THE WORLD OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE - STATISTICS AND EMERGING TRENDS

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Abstract:

It is concluded that health is an important reason for buying organic products. Indian consumers are aware of various organic products and they perceive that it is too expensive comparing with the conventional products. Therefore, it is essential to support the local farmers to produce more organic product and it should be sold in the local market where the small farmers can earn reasonable profit instead of exporting them to various countries. This study focused on consumer behaviour and their willingness to pay towards organic product in general not for a particular product category. It will give a better understanding if we consider the cultural aspects in the study. Awareness has to be created to enable from all the walks of life to use organic product. Government should also provide subsidies for manufacturer of organic product.

Key Words: Organic Products, Cultural Aspects & Local Market

Introduction:

In the twenty first century, sustainability is regarded as most important public health issue (American Public Health Association, 2007). The challenge towards building the healthier communities starts with environmental concern and the combined execution of eco friendly behaviour, since the choices made by consumers regarding the environment have an impact on the quality of life and health for both future and current generations (Royne M. B, Marian and Jenifer 2011). In the current scenario, the concern for creating a healthy and sustainable environment triggered the interest in environmental issues of academics, corporate, media, government and non government organizations. The seriousness of these issues has brought about awareness among consumers to become conscious of their consumption behaviour which causes the green movement, practices and also to perform green behaviour. A person who practices environment behaviour will encourage healthier communities, therefore understanding the concerns with regard to environment amongst the consumers can encompass a significant influence on public well being.

As per American Marketing Association (AMA) -Green marketing involves developing and promoting productions and services that satisfy customers want and need for quality, performance, affordable pricing and convenience without having a detrimental input on the environment hence there is a need to educate the consumers to make them aware of the environmental threats. In today's context consumers worry about world's future and as a result of this most of them have a preference towards environmental friendly products.

The production, trade and consumption of food products have been recognized as critical contributors to many environmental issues among the environmentally important activities (Carmer Tanner, Sybille W. Kase 2003). Regarding food products - green means organically grown food. Organic food purchases are motivated because they are perceived to be healthier, more nutritious, better tasting than non organic foods.

Objectives:

- ✓ To analyse the growth of organic product worldwide.
- ✓ To study the rapid growth of Organic products in India.
- ✓ To measure the Consumer buying preference towards organic products.
- ✓ To analyse the awareness about organic product among general public.
- ✓ To suggest measures.

Research Methodology:

A research design in an overall plan or program of research. A research design or model indicates a plan of action to be carried out in connection with a proposed research work.

Area of Study:

The area of the study is limited to Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of south India, is situated in the western part of the state Tamil Nadu.

Scope of the Study:

This study will help to evaluate the present position of organic products among the existing customers. The study helps to identify the important reason why customers are preferring organic products Simply the study makes a chance to the firm to delight their customers, ultimately for the existence and earnings

in present corporate competition by way of adjusting their products according to the customer needs, if necessary and also to know the strength, weakness, opportunity and threat of the product or the firm.

Statistical Tools Used:

Percentage analysis, One way ANOVA

Review of Literature:

S.No	Citation	Sample	Environment	Method	Conclusions
1	Dr. H. M. Chandrasekar	100 No of Consumers	Mysore	Primary and Secondary Data	The market of organic products need to be improved and dynamic to compete the customer behavior
2	Dr. T. Ponnarsi Asst Professor	25 respondents	Pondicherry	Primary Data	Respondents full aware of the organic products

Analysis and Interpretation:

Age Wise Distribution of the Respondents:

Age	No. of Respondent	Percentage
20-25 years	47	79%
25-35 years	7	11%
35-45 years	0	0%
45 and above	6	10%
Total	60	100

The above table shows that 79% of the respondents are between the age group of 20-25 years, 11% of the respondents are of the age group of 25-35 years, 0% of the respondents are between 35-45 years, and 10% of the respondents are above 45 years of age.

Occupation of the Respondents:

Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
Government Employee	3	5%
Private Employee	20	33%
Student	28	47%
Business	9	15%
Total	60	100

The above table shows that 5% of the respondents are government employee, 33% of the respondents are private employee, 47% of the respondents are students and 15% of the respondents are business persons.

Monthly Income of the Respondents:

Income	Respondents	Percentage
Below 30,000	28	46%
30,000-60,000	16	28%
60,000-1,30,000	10	16%
1,30,000 and above	6	10%
Total	60	100

The above table shows that 46% of the of the respondents monthly income is below 30,000, 28% of the respondents monthly income is between 30,000 to 60,000, 16% of the respondents monthly income is between 60,000 to 1,30,000, and 10 % of the respondents are 1,30,000 and above.

Source of Information Regarding Organic Product:

Source	Respondents	Percentage
Friends/ Relatives	28	47%
Television	19	31%
Newspaper	8	14%
Seminar	0	0%
Not Aware	5	8%
Total	60	100

The above table shows that 47% of the respondents are aware of organic products through friends and relatives, 31% of the respondents are aware through television, 14% of the respondents are aware through newspaper, 0% of the respondents are aware of organic product through seminar and 8% of the respondents are still not aware of organic product.

Demographic Factors (Age, Income and Occupation) and Tenure of Using Organic Products:

H0: There is no significant association between Age and the tenure of using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between Income and the tenure of using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between Occupation and the tenure of using Organic Product.

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups Age	1.460	4	.365	.515	.725
Within Groups	38.940	55	.708		
Total	40.400	59			
Between Groups Income	7.690	4	1.923	2.009	.106
Within Groups	52.643	55	.957	.849	.501
Total	60.333	59	.538		
Between Groups Occupation	2.150	4			
Within Groups	34.833	55	.633	0.849	0.501
Total	36.983	59			

Interpretation:

- ✓ In comparison of Age and Tenure, the calculated Value = .515 Table Value = 2.52, Calculated Value < Table Value, H0 is accepted. There is significant Association between Age and Tenure of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of income and tenure, the calculated value=2.009 The table value = 2.52, calculated value < the table value, HO is accepted. There is significant Association between income and Tenure of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of occupation and tenure, the calculated value=.849 The table value = 2.52, calculated value < the table value, HO is accepted There is significant Association between occupation and Tenure of using Organic Product

Demographic Factors (Age, Income and Occupation) and Type of Using Organic Products:

H0: There is no significant association between Age and the type of using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between income and the type of using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between Occupation and the type of using Organic Products.

Interpretation:

- ✓ In comparison of Age and Type of organic product, the calculated Value = 1.014 Table Value = 2.52, Calculated Value < Table Value, H0 is accepted. There is significant Association between Age and type of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of income and type of using, the calculated value =.449 The table value = 2.52, calculated value < the table value, HO is accepted
- ✓ There is significant Association between income and type of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of occupation and type of using, the calculated value =1.740 The table value = 2.52, calculated value < the table value, HO is accepted
- ✓ There is significant Association between occupation and type of using Organic Products.

Demographic Factors (Age, Income and Occupation) and Source for Using Organic Products:

H0: There is no significant association between Age and the source for using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between income and the source for using Organic Products.

H0: There is no significant association between Occupation and the source for using Organic Products.

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.112	3	.371	.528	.665
Age Within Groups	39.288	56	.702		
Total	40.400	59			
Between Groups	.908	3	.303	.285	.836
Income Within Groups	59.425	56	1.061	2.780	.049
Total	60.333	59	1.598		
Between Groups occupation	4.795	3			
Within Groups	32.189	56	.575		
Total	36.983	59			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

- ✓ In comparison of Age and source for using organic product, the calculated Value = .528 Table Value = 2.75, Calculated Value < Table Value, H0 is accepted. There is significant Association between Age and source of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of income and reason for using, the calculated value = .285 The table value= 2.75, calculated value < the table value, HO is accepted
- ✓ There is significant Association between income and source of using Organic Products.
- ✓ In comparison of occupation and source for using, the calculated value = 2.780 The table value = 2.75, calculated value > the table value, HO is rejected. There is no significant Association between occupation and source of using Organic Products

Findings and Suggestions:

Percentage Analysis:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

- ✓ Majority (79%) of the respondents are between the age group of 20-25 years.
- ✓ Majority (47%) of the respondents are students.
- ✓ Majority (46%) of the respondents monthly income is below 30,000

Source of Information and Attitude of the Respondents:

- ✓ Majority (31%) of the respondents are aware of the organic product through friends and relatives.
- ✓ Majority (48%) of the respondents are using organic product less than a year.
- ✓ Majority 59% of the respondents prefer to buy vegetables.
- ✓ Majority 72% of the respondents are using organic product because it ensures safety and healthy.
- ✓ Majority 44% of the respondents buy through organic outlets.
- ✓ Majority 50% of respondent's economical downturns has increased.
- ✓ Majority 50% of the respondents chooses organic product for the quality of the product.
- ✓ Majority 94% of the respondents feel that organic product is healthy.
- ✓ Majority 56% of the respondents will purchase organic product even though the price rises often.
- ✓ Majority 95% of the respondents feel that organic product is economically friendly.
- ✓ Majority 80% of the respondents believe that increases in green are skeptical about product which are said to be organic.
- ✓ Majority 37% of the respondents trust on scientific evidence in packing.
- ✓ Majority 46% of the respondents feel the information published on product is neither advantages nor disadvantages.
- ✓ Majority 55% are interested in buying non-organic product that have added vitamins and nutrition.
- ✓ Majority 75% of the respondents says that their health have improved by using organic product.

ANOVA:

- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income and occupation with the tenure of using organic product.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income and occupation with the type of using organic product.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income with the source of using organic product, but there is no significant relationship between occupation and the source of using organic product.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income and occupation with the reason of using organic product.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income and occupation with the trust on using organic product.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age, income and occupation with the health benefit of using organic product.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Number of outlets has to be increased.
- ✓ To be sold by self help group and other organisation to improve their standard of living.
- ✓ The quality standard for organic product must be fixed by the government.
- ✓ Uniform pricing has to be fixed by the government.
- ✓ Awareness has to be created to enable from all the walks of life to use organic product.
- ✓ Government should provide subsidies for manufacturer of organic product.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that health is an important reason for buying organic products. Indian consumers are aware of various organic products and they perceive that it is too expensive comparing with the conventional products. Therefore, it is essential to support the local farmers to produce more organic product and it should be sold in the local market where the small farmers can earn reasonable profit instead of exporting them to various countries. This study focused on consumer behaviour and their willingness to pay towards organic product in general not for a particular product category. It will give a better understanding if we consider the cultural aspects in the study. Awareness has to be created to enable from all the walks of life to use organic product. Government should also provide subsidies for manufacturer of organic product.

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